

CALCULATION OF ELECTRICITY LOSSES IN 6/10 KV OVERHEAD AND CABLE POWER TRANSMISSION LINES

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With the growing demand for electricity in rural areas worldwide, improving the efficiency of energy supply and reducing network losses remain critical challenges. These issues are particularly significant for developing countries. Identifying and minimizing energy losses in power networks directly contribute to improving energy efficiency.

The total annual electricity losses in overhead power transmission lines are determined as follows:

$$\Delta W_{xл} = \frac{P_{xл}^2 + Q_{xл}^2}{10^3 \cdot U_{xл}^2} \cdot r_o \cdot L_{xл} + \Delta P_{\text{салт.ўз}} \cdot L_{xл} \cdot T \quad (1)$$

here:

$L_{xл}$ - Length of the overhead lines;

r_o - Specific active resistance of the overhead lines;

$P_{xл}$ and $Q_{xл}$, T - Active and reactive power flowing during the time interval. The time interval for calculations is assumed to be 0.5 hours.

$U_{xл}$ - Average voltage of the network

$P_{\text{сол.из}}$ - Power losses in insulators, determined by the following formula:

$$\Delta P_{\text{сол.из}} = \frac{1000 \cdot P_o}{365 \cdot 24} \quad (2)$$

here: P_o - For a 6 kV line, it is assumed as 0.011 kW/km, representing the power losses per unit length of the insulator.

The electricity loss in cable lines is determined using the following formula:

$$\Delta W_A = 3K_3 \cdot R_{\Sigma} t (I_{\text{мин}}^2 + (I_{\text{макс}}^2 - I_{\text{мин}}^2) \beta) \cdot 10^{-3} \quad (3)$$

here, R_{Σ} - Active resistance of the power transmission line;

K_3 - Equivalent resistance coefficient of the distribution network, determined based on the graph in Figure 3;

t - Calculation period (excluding the line outage time), in hours;

$I_{\text{мин}}$ and $I_{\text{макс}}$ - The minimum and maximum load values of the annual load graphs taken for specific days, in amperes (A);

β - Shape coefficient.

By accurately calculating and analyzing power losses in overhead and cable power transmission lines, the following results can be achieved:

- Development of measures aimed at reducing electricity losses;
- Ensuring balanced load distribution by optimizing load distribution across the lines;
- Regularly inspecting insulators and network resistance to improve their technical condition;
- Analyzing load graphs to efficiently manage low and peak load points.

Thus, by applying methods for loss reduction and calculation techniques in power networks, network efficiency is improved, energy savings are achieved, and economic costs are significantly reduced.

Conclusion. Reducing electricity losses in overhead and cable power transmission lines is a crucial step toward enhancing the efficiency and reliability of power networks. Accurate loss calculations and effective management strategies allow for significant improvements in energy systems.

First, optimizing load distribution and reducing losses ensure better utilization of energy resources, contributing to improved energy efficiency. Second, regular inspection and maintenance of insulators and network resistances enhance the reliability of the power supply system by improving its technical condition.

Moreover, decreasing electricity losses leads to significant economic savings, reducing energy production and distribution costs. These efforts also support sustainable development, particularly in rural areas, by ensuring a stable power supply that fosters economic growth and improves the quality of life.

In conclusion, systematic analysis, the application of advanced loss reduction strategies, and the adoption of innovative technologies are essential for creating a sustainable, efficient, and cost-effective power transmission system.